

Solar Based Medicine Refrigerator

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ABSTRACT

In Today's world global warming is being increasing year by year. In coming years the major problem is depletion of ozone layer which is caused by the release of CFC's. Some of the equipments which are responsible for this effect are refrigerators, AC's. This project is mainly focusing on a solution to control emission of CFC's. So we have focused on refrigerators which release CFC's. Here a mini solar based medicine refrigerator is designed which is cheaper as well as eco-friendly. In this project solar panels are used for charging a Lead Acid Battery (12V, 1.2 Amp hrs), a peltier thermoelectric device which when connected to battery generates cooling effect on one side and heat is dissipated on other side through heat sink, a cooling fan is used for dissipating the heat from the heat sink.

Keyword: CFC's, medicine refrigerator, solar plates, peltier etc.

INTRODUCTION

The Basis for Considering Solar Energy

There are several important reasons for considering solar energy as an energy resource to meet the needs of developing countries. First, most of the countries called developing are in or adjacent to the tropics and have good solar radiation available. Secondly, energy is a critical need of these countries but they do not have widely distributed readily available supplies of conventional energy resources. Thirdly, most of the developing countries are characterized by arid climates, dispersed and inaccessible populations and a lack of investment capital and are thus faced with practically insuperable obstacles to the provision of energy by conventional means, for example, by electrification. In contrast to this solar energy is readily available and is already distributed to the potential users. Fourthly, because of the diffuse nature of solar energy the developments all over the world have been in smaller units which fit well into the pattern of rural economics.

Objectives of the Study

The present study is part of a project in solar energy utilization aimed at the development of one or more prototype units demonstrating the usefulness and economic viability of solar energy for the designed purposes.

The specific objective of the argument in this chapter is to identify an area of solar energy utilization useful to the developing countries of Asia and further, to select a suitable device for development and for a preliminary investigation.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The following figure represents the block diagram of solar refrigerator

Solar panel or solar cell which converts light energy into electrical energy is composed of P-N junctions, where electric current is produced due to the transfer of electrons. During day time the solar plate collects the light and

converts into electricity and this current can be stored in the battery.

The current stored in the battery is only used in the absence of sunlight. And when there is abundant of sunlight the solar plate is directly connected to the refrigerator. The capacity of the battery is 12V and it stores energy which is required in the absence of sunlight.

The ADC which is used to convert the analog or electrical signals from the battery into digital signals. The digital signals are displayed on the LCD. And this LCD displays the maximum voltage present in the battery. The mini refrigerator which has peltier plate inside it acts as a cooling device. The peltier plate is made up of P-N junctions produce cooling effect on one side and heating effect on other side of the plate. The peltier plate works on peltier effect "when current is passed through a junction of two different metals, the heat is either evolved or absorbed at the junction" this is known as peltier effect. A dual mode switch is placed between the battery and the refrigerator, by reversing the polarity we can produce heating or cooling effect inside the refrigerator. i.e., peltier plate can be used as a heating device or cooling device just by reversing the polarity.

Fig1: block diagram

MINI REFRIGERATOR

The mini refrigerator which is used for the storage of medicines in the flood affected areas has a dual mode battery which can be used for both heating and cooling purposes.

Specifications:

- ❖ Cools a beverage from 5V USB Power
- ❖ Stylized as a mini fridge
- ❖ Holds one can
- ❖ Internal LED light
- ❖ USB powered
- ❖ Dimension: 19.4x9x9cm
- ❖ Weight: 362g

SOLAR PANEL

Specifications:

- ❖ Dimensions 45X30 cm.
- ❖ Capacity : 5V
- ❖ Type : photo voltaic
- ❖ 20 watts

PELTIER PLATE

Specifications :

- ❖ Type: TEC1-12726
- ❖ 400W
- ❖ 12V
- ❖ Pellets: 16
- ❖ I_{max} (A): 20
- ❖ Dimensions: 50 x 50 x 3.65mm (2 x 2 x 0.15")
- ❖ Fully sealed for protection against moisture.

LEAD ACID BATTERY

Specifications :

- ❖ Sealed and maintenance free operation.
- ❖ Non-Spillable construction design.
- ❖ 12V 1.3Ah sealed lead acid battery.
- ❖ high quality and reliability.

ADC (Analog to Digital Converter)

An analog to digital converter is a device which converts the readings of a physical quantity into a digital number that represents the quantity's amplitude. In this the result is a sequence of digital values that have converted a continuous-time and continuous-amplitude analog signal to a discrete-time and discrete-amplitude digital signal.

LCD DISPLAY

LCD is also known as liquid crystal display. A liquid crystal display(LCD) is a flat panel display, electronic visual display, or video display that uses the light modulating properties of liquid crystals. LCD's are available to display arbitrary images or fixed images which can be displayed or hidden, such as preset words, digits and seven-segment displays as in a digital clock.

WORKING PROCEDURE:

SOLAR PANEL:

Solar radiations which are emitted by the solar energy are absorbed by the solar panel. Solar panels collect solar radiation from the sun and actively convert that energy to electricity. Solar panels are comprised of several individual solar cells. These solar cells function similarly to large semiconductors and utilize a large-area p-n junction diode. When the solar cells are exposed to sunlight, the p-n junction diodes convert the energy from sunlight into usable electrical energy. The energy generated from photons striking the surface of the solar panel allows electrons to be

knocked out of their orbits and released, and electric fields in the solar cells pull these free electrons in a directional current, from which metal contacts in the solar cell can generate electricity. The more solar cells in a solar panel and the higher the quality of the solar cells, the more total electrical output the solar panel can produce. The conversion of sunlight to usable electrical energy has been dubbed the Photovoltaic Effect.

Solar energy comes from the sunshine. The sun has constant thermonuclear explosions due to the fact that hydrogen atoms are bonded together with helium atoms. Energy brought on by this process that travels to the surface of the earth is known as radiation. Sun power panels convert radiation into electrical energy which can be stored in batteries for later use. Solar panels help to harvest electricity from the sun so that it can be converted into usable energy that is utilized in everyday activities.

A solar panel that has an efficient photovoltaic cell 1/5m within diameter creates approximately several amps at two volts. Many solar panels will not perform and also other solar panels because of atmospheric interference. Some your own solar panels may get direct sunlight all day long while other may just get partial sunlight. Also, solar panels may lose efficiency over the years due to overheating and physical use. The quality of power a unit yields is directly influenced by the quality of the solar panel. The types of materials utilized, the types of technology utilized and the quantity of time the solar panel has been functioning all factor into how efficient the solar panel will be. The main concern for purchasing a solar panel is the dollars/watt ratio. The photovoltaic effect arises from the properties of the p-n junction diode; as such there are no moving parts in a solar panel.

PHOTOVOLTAIC EFFECT:

The Photovoltaic effect is the effect observed when electromagnetic radiation falls on a thin film of one solid deposited on the surface of a dissimilar solid producing a difference in potential between the two materials. The phenomenon in which the incidence of light or other electromagnetic radiation upon the junction of two dissimilar materials, as a metal and a semiconductor, induces the generation of an electromotive force. The conversion of electromagnetic radiation into electric power through absorption by a semiconducting material. Devices based on this effect serve as power sources in remote terrestrial locations and for satellites and other space applications. Photovoltaic--powered calculators and other consumer electronic products are widely available, and solar photovoltaic automobiles and aircraft have been demonstrated.

LEAD ACID BATTERY:

After the conversion of solar energy into electrical energy, the energy has been sent to the Lead-acid Battery. The purpose of Lead-acid Battery is to store the energy for our requirements. Lead Battery is also known as Storage Battery.

PELTIER COOLER:

The electrical energy generated by the solar panel has been sent to the Peltier plate present in the refrigerator. The electrical energy enters to the peltier plate/cooler (or)

thermo electric cooler; the function of peltier plate is to create heat flux between the junctions of two different types of materials. Peltier cooler, heater, or thermoelectric heat pump is a solid-state active heat pump which transfers heat from one side of the device to the other, with consumption of electrical energy, depending on the direction of the current and can be used either for heating or for cooling (refrigeration), although in practice the main application is cooling. It can also be used as a temperature controller that either heats or cools. In peltier plate, a voltage is applied across the device, and as a result, a difference in temperature will build up between the two sides. Thermoelectric coolers operate by the Peltier effect (which also goes by the more general name thermoelectric effect). The device has two sides, and when DC current flows through the device, it brings heat from one side to the other, so that one side gets cooler while the other gets hotter. The "hot" side is attached to a heat sink so that it remains at ambient temperature, while the cool side goes below room temperature. In some applications, multiple coolers can be cascaded together for lower temperature.

WORKING PRINCIPLE OF PELTIER EFFECT:

The peltier effect is also known as thermoelectric effect. The thermoelectric effect is the direct conversion of temperature differences to electric voltage and vice-versa. A thermoelectric device creates voltage when there is a different temperature on each side. Conversely, when a voltage is applied to it, it creates a temperature difference. At the atomic scale, an applied temperature gradient causes charge carriers in the material to diffuse from the hot side to the cold side.

Fig2: Diffusion of charge carriers

This effect can be used to generate electricity, measure temperature or change the temperature of objects. Because the direction of heating and cooling is determined by the polarity of the applied voltage, thermoelectric devices can be used as temperature controllers.

The term "thermoelectric effect" encompasses three separately identified effects: the Seebeck effect, Peltier effect and Thomson effect. Textbooks may refer to it as the Peltier–Seebeck effect. This separation derives from the independent discoveries of French physicist Jean Charles Athanase Peltier and German physicist Thomas Johann Seebeck. Joule heating, the heat that is generated whenever a voltage is applied across a resistive material is related though it is not generally termed a thermoelectric effect. The Peltier–Seebeck and Thomson effects are thermodynamically reversible, whereas Joule heating is not.

PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS AND DATA COLLECTION:

FORMULAE:

PELTIER PLATE:

$$Q = (\pi_B - \pi_A) I$$

Q = peltier heat absorbed by the lower junction per unit time

π_A = peltier coefficient of material A

π_B = peltier coefficient of material B

I = current flowing through the junction

SOLAR PANEL:

To find out how many amps solar panel will deliver in a full sunshine hour we need to do our calculations. We need to convert solar panel output watts to amp hours, so to find the amps we need to divide watts by volts.

$$I \text{ (amps)} = P \text{ (watts)} \div V \text{ (volts)}$$

DATA COLLECTION:

PELTIER PLATE:

The standard data of peltier plate is as follows:

Model Number: TEC1-12726

Material : Ceramic substrate, Sb, Bi, Se, Te, tin

Pellets/count : 16

Dimensions : 50*50*3.65

Max capacity : 400 watts

Imax: 20

Vmax : 15.4

Data required for the analysis have been collected from the performance readings of peltiereffect.

SOLAR PLATE:

Type : Photovoltaic

Maximum voltage : 5V

Capacity : 20W

RESULTS AND CALCULATIONS

PELTIER PLATE:

The materials that are generally used in peltier plate(TEC1-12726) are Pb,Sb,Bi,Te,Se.

The peltier coefficient of the above materials are

$$Pb = 18 \mu V/K$$

$$Sb = 4 \mu V/K$$

$$Bi = -8 \mu V/K$$

$$Te = 500 \mu V/K$$

$$Se = 900 \mu V/K$$

Calculation of number of couples :-

$$\text{couples} = [(count^2)/2]-1$$

$$= [(15^2)/2]-1$$

$$= 128-1$$

$$= 127 \text{ couples}$$

Heat absorbed per unit time :-

$$Q = (\pi_A - \pi_B) I$$

$$= [4 - (-8)]*26$$

$$= 12*26$$

$$= 312 \text{ watts}$$

SOLAR PLATE:

To find how many amps the solar panel will deliver in a full sunshine hour we need to do our calculations. We need to convert the solar panel output watts to amp hours, so to find the amps we need to divide watts by volts.

50 watts (solar panel) divided by the panels nominal voltage 5 volts gives amps per hour. This would be under

exceptionally good circumstances like brilliant sunny day, not hot or cold.

If our total energy requirement is 300 watts, if we convert this to amps(watts ÷ volts) we can work out how many hours we will get from our storage battery.

Conversion of electrical energy of solar panel per hour

$$\text{current} = \frac{\text{watts}}{\text{volts}}$$
$$I = \frac{W}{V}$$
$$= 20/5$$

$$= 4 \text{ amps per hour (on brilliant sunny day)}$$

And the most likely average in usual weather would be closer to 3.4 amps per hour and we can maintain our battery power requirement between 2 and 3 hours.

CONCLUSION

Solar energy is the best and abundantly available form of non-conventional energy source. We have developed a mini refrigerator which uses the solar energy and which has multi usage like heating and cooling. For heating or cooling purpose we are using peltier plate which works on the principle of peltier effect. This system has the advantage of fast chilling, as the plate heats just in the matter of seconds. This system eliminates the refrigerants, which are the main source for the emission of CFC's and HCFC's which in turn

reduces the GREEN HOUSE EFFECT and makes environment pollution free. This system is mainly applicable in preserving medicines, vaccines etc., especially in flood affected areas where there is no power supply.

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